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Deliverable D3.3 - Agora Community Hub outline

WP3 – Living Digital Environment for Knowledge Co-Production

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1. Executive Summary

The objective of this document is to provide an overview of the Agora Community Hub (hereafter, the “Hub”), its main characteristics, potential links to other Agora deliverables and the main Agora project website. Phase I of the initial site is available at www.agoracommunity.org and Phase II will be delivered based on consortium and user feedback and testing. The site will be improved throughout the lifetime of the project and will have legacy beyond the lifetime of the Agora project, as it is built as a weADAPT microsite.

2. Introduction

weADAPT is one of the world’s leading and longest-running collaborative platforms for climate change adaptation. A weADAPT microsite allows organizations and networks to build their own bespoke websites at a fraction of the normal cost and with minimal effort. These individually customized websites benefit from weADAPT in many ways: through its rich knowledge base, active social media channels, popular newsletter, growing levels of website traffic, and ultimately through the connections that allow knowledge products to meaningfully connect to the weADAPT community worldwide beyond the lifetime of any project, ensuring knowledge legacy. Aside from these benefits, this document will provide an outline of the Agora Community Hub, its conception, review, evaluation and eventual design, layout and functionality.

To see the glossary, including definitions of the “co” terms used throughout this document please see Annex 3.

3. Design co-creation, evaluation and iteration

The Hub has gone through several stages of co-creation, evaluation and iteration. This began at workshops at the European Climate Change Adaptation (ECCA) conference (June, 2023) and the Adaptation Futures conference (October, 2023). Participants helped Agora partners identify several priority areas that the Agora Community Hub now aims to address. Suggestions were made for both thematic focus and functionality. For example, suggested data gaps and objectives for the Agora Community Hub included:

- 1) The status of adaptation activities (if they are being planned, ongoing, or completed)
- 2) Information on ongoing or upcoming climate action
- 3) Information on exposure, vulnerability and risk

Based on this feedback, a first draft of design ideas was created and shared with the AGORA project team. The original set of ideas proposed are shared in D3.1: Guidance on design and implementation of the in-person Agora.

Further feedback and iterations with a technical development team allowed us to create a key set of priorities for development, in a phased approach. Graphic designers and website developers then worked on these initial ideas to create new designs of the Hub for further feedback and for official evaluation by Agora reviewers within the Consortium.

4. Responding to feedback and linking to Agora outputs

Discussions with Agora partners and feedback from the evaluation have informed different elements of the Agora Community Hub. For example, there is a general Resources page on the Hub that will serve as a place from which to link key outputs from the project. The various pages planned so far include:

4.1 Explorer maps

To address some of the key recommendations that emerged from conferences sessions and workshops, a key element of the Agora Community Hub is a set of map-based “Explorer” tools (Figure 3). The maps can be filtered to show adaptation projects and case studies, citizen networks, adaptation solutions and organizations working on adaptation. As such, these maps address objectives 1) and 2) above by giving visibility to adaptation activities and to ongoing or upcoming climate action.

4.2 Pilots

A description page of each pilot region was planned within the design phase. The evaluation recommendations also suggested that “each pilot page could feature curated external links pertinent to each pilot, catering to specific countries and languages. These links can be suggested by both pilots and users, fostering a collaborative environment. Additionally, highlight national followers, stakeholders, and organizational profiles on the “Pilots” page. This not only serves as recognition for their involvement but also incentivizes them to register on the platform. A template for pilots to populate these pages would streamline the process.”

All of this feedback has been taken on board and is either implemented or in process of development with Pilot lead partners.

4.3 Networks

Engaging with European national and regional/transnational climate adaptation (knowledge) platforms (CAPs) is a component of Task 4.4. This has begun with a number of European Commission (EC)-funded projects and the EU Mission Adaptation Community of Practice collaborating on a webinar. This has supported the continuation of a [CAP community of practice](#) to

identify opportunities to work together and enter into a dialogue with national and regional/transnational CAPs.

The prime interest so far has been informing these CAPs about the EC projects, their respective intentions, and seeking CAPs views as to how best to engage them as part of the respective EC-funded projects and the Mission’s Community of Practice. This network of CAPs will now be hosted on the Agora Community Hub. Supporting this action, the evaluation also recommended to: “integrate and strengthen the connection, if possible, with national climate adaptation platforms within the Digital AGORA [Agora Community Hub], taking advantage from the trust that they built with local stakeholders and their knowledge about how to engage them.”

4.4 Catalogues and toolboxes

Partners have collated many resources throughout the Agora project including methods for citizen and stakeholder engagement. For example, a [survey](#) has been conducted to map citizen engagement initiatives (CEIs) on climate change adaptation in Europe (WP1). The many initiatives collated here will be catalogue on the Hub in the form of a searchable Toolbox. Additionally, functionality on the website to enable uploading content in large batches, will ensure that the number of CEIs already collated can be easily uploaded and quickly accessible by the public.

4.5 Academies

To address objective 3) above, there are two Academies planned in the project. Both are currently under development but there will be links to them from the Agora Community Hub. The current active working page for the **Digital Academy to Access and Use Climate Data and Monitor Climate Risks** is <https://agoradigitalacademy.dataclimate.com/>.

4.6 News and events

As recommended by the evaluation, the “News & Events” and “About” pages on the Hub’s original design were removed to prevent overlap and duplication with the project website’s “News” and “About” sections. Instead, direct links to the project website’s respective pages have been included on the Hub.

5. Agora Community Hub website

The menu of the Hub will reflect links to outputs as described above as well as links to the Agora project website.

AGORA Explorer	Pilots	Resources	Information
Case Studies	Germany	Toolboxes	Team
Solutions	Spain	Academies	Terms of use
Citizens Networks	Italy	Climate data	Privacy Policy
Organizations	Sweden	FAQ's	Cookie Notice

Figure 1: Footer of the Agora Community Hub

Taking into account recommendations of the evaluation, many of the images in the website design, especially the homepage (Figure 2) have been updated. This includes reducing the extensive use of map imagery (except in the Explorer tools), which may be less appealing to the citizen and non-academic audience of the Hub.

The Explorer tools allow the visualization of projects, solutions, citizen networks and organizations. These elements can be searched by topic, theme, network, content type or country (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Homepage

Figure 3: Explorer tool

As mentioned above, the Resources page will ensure Agora deliverables and outputs are accessible to the Agora Community Hub audience. This will showcase various networks, toolboxes, Academies, and links to data visualizations and tools as they are developed (Figure 4).

Recommendations from the evaluation provided further guidance on imagery. To reduce potential bias and discrimination the idea of asking users to upload images related to climate adaptation was explored. It was suggested that “this approach not only promotes inclusivity but also allows participants to express themselves through images that represent their interests and engagement with the topic.” In advance of suggesting this to users, the Hub uses avatars by default within personal profiles (Figure 5) and will then encourage the uploading of images related to climate adaptation “to foster a sense of community and shared purpose among participants, reinforcing the overarching theme of the platform” as recommended by the reviewers.

Figure 4: The Resources page

Figure 5: A personal profile

Annex 1. Glossary

Within AGORA, a common Glossary is being developed so that all key terms related to climate change adaptation are used to refer to the same concepts, and these are applied in all activities ranging from face-to-face events within the Pilot regions to all the digital tools. Therefore, in all the learning journeys included in the Digital Academies, as well as within the Digital AGORA the concepts are always used respecting the definitions provided in the AGORA Glossary. While this final document will be presented at the end of the project, the main concepts used throughout have been agreed upon and are a core part of the Glossary, so have been included in this document within Annex 1 to provide an overarching framework for reference.

Term	Definition
Co-Creation	Collaboratively creating outputs like tools or policy recommendations. A process that can add value and increase innovative potential through intentional experience design

